

Effect of Chemotherapy on Protein Level of Under Treatment Cancer Sufferers

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cancer staging is an important aspect of cancer management and directly affects the treatment plan of the patient. There are several protein tumour markers that helps in the diagnosis as well as prognosis of cancer patients.

Aim: The current study aims to evaluate the total protein value from the serum samples of selected cancer patients and see any pattern with different stages of patients.

Materials & Method: Total proteins were measured by IR-VS spectroscopy method and compared in different patients.

Result: The spectrophotometric analysis of the collected serum samples showed that chemotherapy induced total protein loss is associated with dysregulation in serum proteins and electrolytes. Total protein is a significant marker that can help determine the tumour staging in cancer patients and thus can act as a prognostic marker also. It is a simple, non-invasive and cost effective method of analysis.

KEYWORDS: Cancer, Total protein, Markers, Spectrophotometry, Tumour, Chemotherapy

INTRODUCTION

Role of Protein Value in Cancer

Protein with altered expression levels in cancer are involved in protein synthesis and degradation signalling and metabolic pathways DNA repair apoptosis and other cellular processes whose alterations cause tumour development and progression. Enhanced cell growth and repair as well as improvements in blood clotting and infection fighting. Human cancers oncogenes often induce profound and rapid cell growth associated with an increase in overall protein synthesis. The synthesis of proteins can be controlled at many levels including through the production of new ribosomes.

Translationally Controlled Tumour Protein (TCTP)

Another important class of tumour protein is the translationally controlled tumour protein (TCTP) that has been extensively studied. There are three type of this protein namely P²¹, Q²³ and P²³ respectively (Ulrich-Axel Bommer *et al.*, 2004) and is found to be involved in many biological functions and disease processes including cancer in all eukaryotic organisms predominantly in the response to cellular stresses such as oxidative stress, heat shock, genotoxic stress, imbalance of ion metabolism etc. TCTP acts as an anti-apoptotic protein, and it is involved in DNA-damage repair and in cellular autophagy and cell division (Ulrich-Axel Bommer *et al.*, 2017). Tumour Infiltrating Lymphocytes are immune cells produced in response to tumour and are proteins in nature and have been found to be very useful diagnostic as well as prognostic markers of tumour. There is clear evidence that the immune system plays an essential role in tumour defence. By determining tumour-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs), the individual immunological response becomes more apparent and measurable. In breast cancer, high levels of TILs are associated with a more favourable clinical course (Whiteside *et al.*, 2022).

The study successfully indicated the role of these signalling proteins as useful biomarkers for tumour classification and predicting outcome in gastric cancer patients. Another group of scientists explored exosomes proteins as potential biomarkers for tumour development and progression. It has been found that exosomes proteins can in fact regulate tumour development and their microenvironment and therefore can provide insight into exosome generation and tumour related activities including angiogenesis, metastasis etc. and thus are extremely useful biomarkers for cancer diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment.

Rasouli *et al.*, 2005 studied the electro-phoretic pattern of blood proteins in various cancer patients. The study aimed to evaluate the difference in protein pattern in different cancers to check if there is a specific pattern of proteins that can be correlated with cancer types and used as biomarker for diagnosis. The study was done using colorimetric techniques to quantify total protein and albumin in cancer patients and densitometry was used to do the quantitative analysis of each protein fraction.

Uni-variate analysis as well as multiple logistic regression analysis revealed a strong correlation between serum protein profiles and prevalence of cancer thus indicating its biomarker potentiality. The best parameters to distinguish between malignant and healthy states were alpha (1)-globulin, total protein, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, and the ratio of albumin to globulin. Explored the differences in total protein content between the saliva and serum of female breast cancer patients and female healthy individuals and the result showed statistically significant difference in the total protein content in both saliva and serum in breast cancer patients and healthy group. Thus, they supported the role of protein biomarker in the diagnosis and prognosis of cancer patients and warranted further research work.

MATERIAL & METHOD

Sample Collection:

Volunteers (Multiple Myeloma) blood samples were collected in plane tubes (Red cap), 2 ml from each. With Institutional Ethical Committee approval from JNCH & RC, Bhopal (**Ethical approval ref. no.1013C/JNCH/RES /22/05/2024**), Samples are collected from Department of Pathology JNCH & RC, Bhopal.

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE APPROVAL; IES approval will be taken before starting the research work.
INFORMED CONSENT; Informed consent from will be signed by each subject enrolled for the study.

PRINCIPLE:

Protein in the sample reacts with copper (II) ion in alkaline medium forming a coloured complex that can be measured by spectrophotometry.

Sample: Serum

PROCEDURE:

1. Pipette into labelled test tubes:

REAGENTS	BLANK	STANDARD	SAMPLE
Distilled water	20 µl	-----	-----
Protein Standard (S)	-----	20 µl	-----
Sample	-----	-----	20 µl
Reagent (A)	1.0ml	1.0ml	1.0ml

2. Mix thoroughly and let stand the tubes for 10 minutes at room temperature.
3. Read the absorbance A) of the Standard and the Sample at **545 nm** against the Blank. The colour is stable for at least 2 hours.

CALCULATIONS:

The protein concentration in the sample is calculated using the following general formula

$$\frac{A \text{ sample} \times C \text{ standard}}{A \text{ standard}} = C \text{ Sample}$$

REFERENCE VALUES:

Serum adults normal range.

AMBULATORY	64-83g/L
RECUMBENT	60-78g/L

OBSERVATIONS

S.NO	CODE	AGE	SEX	T.P	CANCER STAGE	SPE DIAGNOSIS
1	P1	54	F	6.9	II	Polyclonal Gammopathy Disease
2	P5	48	F	7.3	III	Multiple myeloma
3	P9	67	F	7.7	II	Multiple myeloma
4	P11	68	F	5.8	II	Relapse of Disease
5	P12	44	F	6.8	II	Myeloma Protein Of M-Type
6	P15	38	F	6	III	Normal Band Pattern
7	P17	55	F	6	III	Multiple Myeloma
8	P19	53	F	5.2	III	Depletion of Stem Cell in The Bone Muscle
9	P20	64	F	8.5	III	Remission Phase
10	P21	42	F	8.3		Myeloma Protein Of M-Type
11	P22	73	F	8.1	II	The Quantification of Myeloma Protein Is Low Hence the Patient in Rabin Phase
12	P23	73	F	4.8	II	There Is No Gammopathy There Is No Evidence of Myeloma Protein
13	P25	71	F	4.05	III	Disease Involved in Bone and Other Major Vital Organ Like Kidney- Lungs
14	P28	53	F	5.4	III	Multiple myeloma
15	P31	38	F	10	III	Myeloma Protein Of M-Type
16	P36	60	F	5	III	Multiple myeloma
17	P37	22	F	7.1	II	There Is No Evidence of Gammopathy Normal Band Pattern

Table.02: Showing 'Total protein' values of Female individuals on chemotherapy with stage of Cancer and their Serum Protein Electrophoresis (SPE) results.

Graph: 01 Showing Total protein values of Male patients (On Chemotherapy) with age 35 to 79 years.

Graph: 02 Showing Total protein values of Female patients (On Chemotherapy) with age 22 to 73 years.

RESULTS

Blood serum samples of cancer patients in our study group was taken to check the total protein level and its correlation with Serum protein electrophoresis impressions. Especially female group showed a mild reduction in total protein values. Our results show that patients with severe Multiple Myeloma had pronounced changes in serum protein and electrolytes and increased incidence of abnormal serum protein pattern shown in (Table.01 & 02). Maximum patients covered in our study are belongs to stage III cancer. The changes in the total protein showed a positive correlation with the changes in serum protein and electrolyte levels. A similar trend was seen in both the groups (20) Male & (17) Female. Taken together our results suggest that chemotherapy induced total protein loss is associated with dysregulation in serum proteins and electrolytes. Cancer treatment includes chemotherapy, radiation

therapy, biological therapy, surgery or a combination of two or more of these therapeutic options. All of these treatment options are aimed to eradicate the cancer cells that exist in the patient's body. Chemotherapy targets and destroys all rapidly dividing cells including cancerous and normal cells. As a result chemotherapy affects the body's normal organs, tissues and decreased protein level in the body. The serum total protein levels of the elderly possibly decrease gradually with aging. However, serum total protein levels are not suitable as a uniform reference standard for the elderly at different ages and genders.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

The total protein serum test measures the total amount of albumin and globulin in the blood. Values below the normal threshold usually are associated with nutritional deficiency, liver, kidney disease and Cancer. Elevated total protein values can be a marker of chronic inflammation or malignancies such as multiple myeloma. A high total protein level could indicate dehydration or a certain type of cancer, such as multiple myeloma, that causes protein to accumulate abnormally. If the result of a total protein test is abnormal, further tests will be needed to identify which proteins are too high or too low. This will enable an accurate diagnosis to be made. Protein with altered expression levels in cancer are involved in protein synthesis and degradation signalling and metabolic pathways DNA repair apoptosis and other cellular processes whose alterations cause tumour development and progression. Enhanced cell growth and repair as well as improvements in blood clotting and infection fighting. Human cancers oncogenes often induce profound and rapid cell growth associated with an increase in overall protein synthesis. Taken together our results suggest that chemotherapy induced total protein loss is associated with dysregulation in serum proteins and electrolytes. However, it's crucial to note that individuals undergoing chemotherapy may require increased protein intake to support tissue repair and fight infection

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